

An Overview of Ponding in Tensile Membrane Structures

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Abstract

Tensile membrane structures (TMS) are efficient and aesthetically pleasing systems that are widely used for various long-span applications. The predominant design consideration for TMS is to prevent the tearing of the membrane fabric under external loads such as wind or snow. However, design considerations such as ponding are also crucial for maintaining the safety, functionality, and durability of these structures. Ponding refers to the accumulation of water on the membrane surface, causing additional deformation and increased loading on the fabric. In TMS design, ponding is mitigated by ensuring that an adequate slope is provided, to avoid water or snow accumulation, by adjusting either the boundary conditions or the applied prestress, or both. However, seeding events such as heavy rainfall or snow, reduction in prestress due to creep, improper maintenance, etc. can lead to progressive ponding. There have been several incidents of small-to-large-scale TMS failure due to ponding, which show the real-life implications of this problem. The objective of this work is, therefore, to provide an introductory study on the effects of ponding on TMS, including the development of design strategies and an examination of the various seeding events. An integrated framework is developed in order to assess different TMS for ponding based on code guidelines. The susceptibility of different TMS shapes to failure by tearing or by ponding is demonstrated through different case studies, covering both basic and complex shapes.

Keywords: ponding, tensile membrane structures, tensile fabric, drainage, slacking

1. Introduction

Tensile membrane structures (TMS) are popularly used as lightweight and sustainable applications, and these structures notably differ from other conventional structures primarily due to their inherent flexibility and large deflection characteristics. The design of TMS largely aims to prevent the tearing of the membrane fabric when subjected to external loads. However, in order to guarantee a safe design, other key design considerations must also be taken into account. One of these factors is to prevent the occurrence of ponding, which is the buildup of water on the membrane surface. Over time, this accumulation can increase, placing additional load on the fabric, potentially leading to a failure of the fabric. Historically, research on TMS has focused on the development of various form-finding methods to determine the initial equilibrium shape [1]. Additional research has examined the load analysis of these structures, considering their nonlinear behavior [2] and the occurrence of wrinkling [3]. Overall, research on the large-scale design of TMS to address ponding is limited. Historically, membrane structures have frequently failed due to ponding, affecting both large- and small-scale TMS. Recent examples include failures in Kiewit in 2011 [4], Toyota Pavillion in 2007 [5] and the Jabalpur and Rajkot airports in India in 2024 [6]. Furthermore, the increasing frequency and intensity of climate-related disasters, such as heavy rainfall and storms across the globe, pose additional challenges for effective TMS design [7].

The major work on ponding have been largely analytical studies on flat circular air-inflated structures [8, 9, 10]. These works focused majorly on finding the critical depth and stability assessment. Other works have approached the problem using finite element solvers [11, 5, 12, 13, 7]. Most studies have focused on simpler shapes but still required significant computational efforts. This is due to the complex interaction between

hydrostatic loads and the membrane's nonlinear behavior, both of which must be accounted for simultaneously during the analysis.

Current code provisions and guidelines for the design of TMS [14, 15] provide limited instructions for the evaluation of ponding. The methodology for assessment is often unclear, with few practical guidelines for implementation. Overall, a general implementation guideline on mitigating ponding for real-life projects is lacking in the existing literature. This study, therefore, aims to implement an integrated framework for the assessment of ponding in TMS. Additionally, the effect of different seeding events on ponding stability is explored and investigated. The paper is structured as follows: Firstly, a brief summary and a general review of ponding are provided, covering its mechanisms, modeling strategies, and relevant code provisions. In the subsequent section, the study proposes and implements an integrated framework to quantify ponding during the design of TMS. The proposed method are then tested on simple and complex TMS shapes, wherein different seeding events are also explored.

Figure 1: Ponding induced failure at (a) Rajkot airport ([16]) (b) Jabalpur airport ([17]), India.

2. Ponding

Ponding is the accumulation of water on the membrane surface, which may progressively increase and lead to fabric tearing and structural failure (Fig. 2(a)). It is initiated by an initial depression, which may be caused by different “seeding events” such as snow loading, imperfections in the design, loss of prestress and improper boundary conditions, design flaws, improper or inadequate drainage and poor maintenance [9]. In this section, an overview and review of ponding in TMS is provided along with the different challenges faced.

2.1. Mechanism of ponding

At the outset, an initial depression on the surface has to be present due to a seeding event. An improper slope of the membrane surface can also lead to water accumulation, preventing proper run-off and drainage of both rainwater and snow as shown in Fig. 2(b). This continuous buildup of snow or rainwater, increases the sagging deformation and creates a local bagging effect [7]. The local depression is due to the large deflection behaviour of these very flexible structures under the gravity of accumulated snow or rainwater. Ponding is therefore a nonlinear behaviour where the membrane deformation and the applied loading are coupled together. The ponded water acts as a hydrostatic load acting normally on the wet surface area further deforming the membrane fabric. In the case where the membrane is stiffer, some of the excess water can drain resulting in a smaller stable pond [4]. The water catchment can also change with respect to time due to surface run-off because of heavy rain [11]. In the case of inflated membrane structures, the stability of the ponded area is described by the ability of the internal pressure and stiffness to maintain the overall shape. The localized addition of snow or water, should not cause excessive deformation such that a progressive collection takes place [7]. Additionally, the affect of wind and rain on ponded catchments on TMS can also lead to coupling effects that can lead to failure [12].

So far, research works on ponding have focused primarily on studying the ponding deformation profile for simple shapes [5], and on numerical methods for the hydrostatic load analysis [5]. Tuan [8] provided analytical and experimental studies on the ponding of circular membranes, under hydrostatic pressure. Using analytical models, it was found that the critical depth for ponding is a function of the initial imperfection, internal pressure (for pneumatic structures), height/span, density of the fluid and weight of the fabric [9, 8, 10]. Additionally, ponding can also cause failure in the supporting structure [18]. The overall ponding stability is described by a critical depth, which is a function of the initial imperfection, prestress etc. [18]

Figure 2: TMS surface (a) with ponding over a catchment (b) with low inclination

2.2. Numerical modeling

Ahmadi and Glockher [9] formulated an analytical model to study the ponding collapse of air-inflated spherical membranes. Tuan [8] used an analytical approach to predict the deflection of hydrostatic water accumulation on inflated structures. A fourth-order Runge-Kutta integration method was used along with finite element method. Other analytical approaches to model ponding used iterative coupled solvers [5, 12, 13]. Early work on ponding stability focused on the flat circular membranes and air-supported pneumatic structures [8, 9, 10] with most of the work done being analytical in nature [8, 9, 10, 19]. Advanced coupling solvers were employed by Narayanan *et al.* [12] to model the effect of the ponded water alongwith wind loading, using CFD analysis and a volume constraint solver. Studies on the rupture of the membrane fabric including the failure of the fabric were reported by Samy *et al.* [7]. They used the vector form intrinsic finite element method to model the rupture propagation on TMS and pneumatic structures due to ponding. Bown *et al.* [11] used a time-stepping approach for modeling runoff on larger membrane structures using their TMS design software. The runoff was modeled with shallow water equations, but the work was limited and did not robustly address coupling issues. Most of these studies focused on simple membrane shapes and simplifying assumptions on the initial seeding events.

2.3. Design and challenges

The design of TMS primarily focuses on making sure that the principal stresses on the membrane due to external loads, remains within allowable limits. However, hydrostatic pressure caused due to the accumulated water in ponded regions can lead to increased stress levels in the membrane exceeding those experienced under “normal” loading conditions. Current design/construction guidelines primarily emphasize on maintaining a proper slope and drainage. A summary of different guidelines from current standards is given in Table 1. It is evident that the primary recommendation across all codes is to ensure that a proper slope and sufficient drainage is provided. Conventionally, a ponding check is suggested [20] that involves applying a uniform load, such as a snow load, to the TMS surface while considering reduced material properties and prestress. After the application of the load, regions with minimal slope or areas prone to water accumulation are then identified. CEN [20] also states that ponding within certain limits may be permitted if it meets strength and serviceability requirements. Furthermore, the Tensinet guideline [21] recommends the surface slope to be checked to ensure proper drainage for rain and melted snow run-off. An integrated framework is therefore required to evaluate the risk of specific regions to ponding, determine its allowance and ensure proper drainage. In many geographical regions, external factors such as snow accumulation are also highly dependent on proper

maintenance, requiring inputs of the designer based on the analysis of the slope. The lack of robust integrated solutions overall makes it difficult to accurately assess ponding in these structures. A valuable framework for designers should automate the identification and assessment of weak zones prone to ponding.

Table 1: Summary of codes and guidelines with respect to ponding

Document	Type	Guideline
ASC-55 [14]	Standard	Potential of membrane for ponding. At minimum, maintain positive drainage under all service loads.
CEN/TS 19102 [20]	Technical Spec. (Pre-Standard)	Verified for ponding. Ponding under external loads is accepted if serviceable and structural integrity limits is proofed using iterative analysis. Reduction in material properties and prestress.
Tensinet: European Design Guideline [21]	Guideline	Verify ponding under snow loads. Consider the surface slope to ensure proper drainage. Check for low surface inclination.

3. Proposed methodology

This section proposes a framework to assess the TMS slope and its susceptibility to ponding. The methodology is developed to comply with the guidelines as given in Sec. 2.3.. The integrated framework is later demonstrated on various examples in Sec. 4..

3.1. Analysis of TMS

TMS are flexible structures whose equilibrium shape is a function of the applied prestress and boundary condition. Initially a form-finding step is required to find the initial shape of these structures for an applied prestress input. Subsequently, the form-found shape is then used for the load analysis step. During load analysis the major load cases are wind or snow loading. Form-finding is done by solving the equilibrium equations through a minimization of the following objective function:

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \underset{\mathbf{x}}{\operatorname{argmin}} f_{UW} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_m} \sum_{j=1}^3 W_i^j (L_i^j)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} c_{w_i} (c_{l_i})^2 \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x}^* represents the coordinates of the form-found shape; W_i^j and L_i^j denote the weight and the j th side length ($j = 1, 2, 3$), respectively, of the i th element; c_{w_i} represents the cable weight; and c_{l_i} represents the boundary cable length. These weights are related to the target membrane prestress σ_w^0 , σ_f^0 and cable prestress n^0 [22]. The form-found prestressed state is then used as the initial shape for load analysis given as the discretized solution of solving the minimum of the total potential energy, whereby the strain is modified in the instances where an element is either ‘wrinkled’ or ‘taut’. The fabric is oriented along the warp and fill directions where the orthotropic material properties are defined by the Young’s moduli and the Poisson’s ratios.

The load analysis is performed by minimizing the following total potential energy formulation:

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \underset{\mathbf{u}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \pi = \int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^T \mathbf{C} \tilde{\mathbf{E}} dA + \int_{\Omega} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^T \mathbf{S}^0 dA - \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{P} \mathbf{u} dA \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{u}^* is the displacement under the external traction load \mathbf{P} , $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$ represents the modified Green-Lagrange strains and \mathbf{S}^0 represents the initial prestress. The modification of the strain is done for elements that have wrinkled or slacked [3]. An orthotropic material constitutive tensor (\mathbf{C}) is used which comprises of E_w and

E_f to denote the elastic moduli in the warp and fill directions, respectively, and G for the shear modulus.

3.2. Proposed integrated framework

This section develops and integrates methods into a form-finding and load analysis workflow to assess the following under snow load and other seeding events:

1. Evaluating the slope/inclination of the surface
2. Assessing ponding formation and its stability

These objectives are achieved by considering the influence of surface slopes or slope inclination on the discretized deformed shape under the snow load. Secondly a “basin-based” algorithm is used to identify the presence of depressions or basins on the membrane. The overall ponding stability of these depressions is then assessed by performing a hydrostatic loading analysis. These assessments are done for various seeding events that can initiate ponding on the structure.

The slope based framework is done to identify regions having low slope in the case of flatter surfaces that may not provide sufficient drainage to snow and water accumulation. This aids the designer in pinpointing regions for maintenance and mitigation planning. Additionally, the ponding basin algorithm identifies areas where water accumulates during a specific seeding event and evaluates the overall pond stability. Finally, the structural stresses under hydrostatic load are analyzed to determine whether some acceptable ponding is allowed as outlined in Sec. 2.3.

3.2.1. Inclination assessment

The slope-based approach follows the recommendations available in different guidelines and standards for TMS. These recommendations highlight the need to identify regions on the membrane structure that do not have sufficient slope needed for drainage. On the other hand, not all regions that have a very low slope may accumulate snow or rain as the region may be locally anticlastic. Therefore, regions which can be attributed as being the vulnerable portions of the TMS under a seeding event are given by

$$\mathcal{S} = \{n : n \in N; \mathcal{K}_n^1 > 0; \mathcal{K}_n^2 > 0; \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_n \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 < \theta_a\} \quad (3)$$

where, a node which is flagged as being “vulnerable” satisfies these two conditions:

- Minimum and maximum principal curvatures are positive (\mathcal{K}_n^1 and $\mathcal{K}_n^2 > 0$). This condition denotes the local formation of a convex function.
- Normal of the surface at the node $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_n$ with respect to the vertical axis, has an inclination lesser than the allowable slope θ_a (Fig. 2b). This indicates that there is no proper slope provided in the ponded region.

Furthermore, strongly connected components of the graph-based representation of the mesh is used to make sure to subdivide the nodes in set \mathcal{S} to different sub-groups. Additionally, the subgroups are triangulated and the surface area (A^s) is calculated:

$$A^s = \sum_i^{N_s} A_i \quad (4)$$

where A_i is the area of N_s number of elements formed from the triangulated elements with nodes in \mathcal{S} .

3.2.2. Ponding stability assessment

The basin-based approach identifies locations that have developed basins on the membrane surface following the seeding procedure. A priority queue-based ‘flood-fill’ algorithm is employed here to identify the places on the membrane that have become depressions and can accumulate water. Likewise, the mesh connection is

employed to partition the set into subgroups or sub-basins by finding the strongly connected components of the equivalent graph. The surrounding elements for each sub-basin is then used to find the free surface and the consequent reference datum. The places where the water surface touches the mesh are triangulated, and the volume v is calculated using the projected area and the average height from the local free surface elevation given as

$$v = \sum_i^N A_i^p h_i^{avg} \quad (5)$$

where A^p and h^{avg} are the projected area and average height of each element with respect to the sub-basin reference datum. Hydrostatic loading is subsequently applied to each sub-basin to assess the stability of the ponded depression using an equivalent load approach predicated on the intersection of the elements with the surface of the accumulated water. The loading vector \mathbf{f} locally defined on each element is found by [5]:

$$\mathbf{f} = \int \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x})^T \rho g h(\mathbf{x}) dA \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x})$ is the shape function of the element, ρ is the density of water, g is the gravitational constant and $h(\mathbf{x})$ is the positive depth with respect to the reference free surface of the sub-basin. The distorted structure is subsequently evaluated using the flood-fill algorithm to determine the presence of any basins or deformations under hydrostatic loading. Likewise, additional critical metrics, including the maximum principal stresses and deformation, can be evaluated.

3.2.3. Integrated framework

The framework integrates the form-finding and load analysis given in Sec. 3.1. and the inclination and ponding assesment given in Secs. 3.2.1. and 3.2.2. respectively. The overall integration is achieved through the following steps:

Step 1: Form-finding and analysis

1. Perform form-finding using UWM to achieve the target prestress and cable prestress.
2. Conduct load analysis on the form-found shape under snow loading during a seeding event.

Step 2: Inclination check

1. Identify nodes on the deformed surface that satisfy Eq. 3, for θ_a and flag them.
2. Group the flagged regions into sub-areas and calculate their respective areas A^s .

Step 3: Ponding and stability assessment

1. Identify and categorize ponding basins on the deformed surface, then calculate their volume v .
2. Establish local sub-basin reference datums and compute hydrostatic loading.
3. Reanalyze the deformed shape under only hydrostatic loading.
4. Re-identify ponding basins and determine principal stresses.

4. Numerical analysis

In this section, the integrated framework is demonstrated for different case studies. The initial form-finding and load analysis is done using the UWM and modified energy based minimization methods as detailed in Sec. 3.1.. The analysis is then integrated with the ponding assesment methods detailed in Sec. 3.2.. The principal curvatures on the discretized membrane is found using an approximate method as detailed in [3]. All the structures have isotropic properties with E_w and E_f equal to 600 kN/m while ν is 0.4. The steel cable elements have a cross sectional area of $1.13 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$. The factored fabric strength is assumed to be at 9

Figure 3: Case A: Square conic (a) Initial depression under snow loading (b) Ponding stability under hydrostatic loading

kN/m^2 . The material properties and prestress are halved while performing the analysis. The results are shown with respect to the ponded region and prestress applied. The examples are demonstrated using MATLAB on an AMD Ryzen 7 3.2 Ghz CPU with 16 Gb memory. In all the examples, the deformed shape under the snow seeding event and the hydrostatic loading is shown. The basins initially produced from the seeding event are depicted in grey, whereas those resulting from hydrostatic loading are represented in blue.

4.1. Example 1

The first example involves a square-based cone with a base width of 5 meters and an inner radius of 1.5 meters. Two case examples are considered with heights of 2 meters (Case A) and 1.3 meters (Case B). In Case A, the design prestress is considered to be 4 kN/m in both the warp and fill directions. In the second scenario, the design prestress is considered to be 2 kN/m . It is important to note that in both instances, the applied target prestress and material characteristics are halved (Sec. 2.3.). The initial form-found shape is non-minimal and therefore non-isotropic. An initial depression is observed due to a seeding snow load event of 1 kN/m^2 , as illustrated in Fig. 3(a). Thus, the initial depression is utilized to implement hydrostatic loading as outlined in Sec. 3.2. As shown in Fig. 3(b), the structure demonstrates stability due to the hydrostatic loading and returns to a non-depressed state. This indicates that the depression resulting from a the snow load is stable. In Case B, the mean prestress after form-finding is found to be isotropic, with the initial snow load resulting in a depression as illustrated in Fig. 4(b). Upon the application of hydrostatic force, the structure ultimately maintains a ponded depression as illustrated in Fig. 4(b). The ponded volume at the conclusion is 0.036 m^3 ,

Figure 4: Case B: Square conic (a) Initial depression under snow loading (b) Ponding stability under hydrostatic loading

Figure 5: (a) Ridge valley structure (b) Incline check for $\theta_a = 25^\circ$ (c) Incline check for $\theta_a = 30^\circ$

with an area of 5.035 m^2 , and the maximum principal stresses induced by the ponded water is 2.42 kN/m^2 . Consequently, in this specific case, the ponding is permissible with regards to the fabric strength.

4.2. Example 2

This second example features a ridge-valley TMS having a dimension of 14 m with a height of 3 m. Cables run down the valleys and ridges of the structure as shown in red in Fig. 5(a) while the other boundary points are fixed. The specified prestress is set at 5 kN/m , with the cable tension forces maintained at 50 kN . The form-derived configuration for this prestress is illustrated in Fig. 5(a). The structure is evaluated under snow loading, and the total slope is analyzed as detailed in Sec. 3.2.. The findings for the permissible slope $\theta_a = 25^\circ$ and 30° are presented in Figs. 5(b) and (c) accordingly, where the flagged elements are highlighted in orange. Also, the area A^s of the sloped regions for both cases is 12.61 m^2 and 28.49 m^2 , respectively. It is seen that increasing the value of θ_a expands the area having an inclination lower than the maximum allowable slope. This tool assists designers in identifying structural slopes that are more susceptible to snow buildup, facilitating the planning of maintenance and mitigation solutions.

Another seeding event is examined, where the middle valley cable experiences a relaxation of its prestress in conjunction with the applied snow loading. The average prestress on the structure post form-finding is isotropic. The first depression caused by snow loading and subsequent relaxation is illustrated in Fig. 6(b), which is then utilized as the initial depression for hydrostatic loading. The ultimate ponded depression on the structure is seen in Fig. 6(c), including a ponded volume v of 0.059 m^3 using Eq. 5. Under the hydrostatic loading due to the ponded water, the membrane fabric experiences a maximum principal stress of 8.40 kN/m , close to the fabric's tearing strength if the pond continues to enlarge. This example therefore illustrates the

Figure 6: Ridge valley (a) Initial depression under snow loading and cable seeding events (b) Ponding stability under hydrostatic loading

necessity of accounting for various seeding events, such as the loss of prestress or cable tension, which can alter the overall features and behavior of the structural system. In this example, it was shown that the loss of prestress in the inner cable leads to the formation of ponding and snow, as seen in Fig. 6(b), followed by water accumulation (Fig. 6(c)), potentially causing the overall fabric to rupture.

5. Conclusion

This study initially presents an overview of ponding in tensile membrane constructions. An integrated methodology for evaluating the inclination and ponding susceptibility of TMS under various initial events is presented. The entire process offers the designer a framework that adheres to existing requirements and delivers a comprehensive assessment of potential dangers related to ponding. This is accomplished through the processing of the deformed shape, assessing the overall curvature, and identify the local basins where water can accumulate. The approach is illustrated via two distinct case studies examining various seeding events. The comprehensive metrics and graphical representations provided to the designer enable the implementation of calculated and remedial measures throughout the design process of these structures. These tools help in addressing the issues of snow accumulation and ponding.

Future study will incorporate other factors in the analysis including volume preservation constraints, during the application of hydrostatic force. The incorporation of these tools as open-source tool will enhance engagement and utilization by designers.

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